

ASSESSMENT OF THE ATTITUDES OF FARMERS TOWARDS FRUITS AND VEGETABLE CONSUMPTION AMONG RURAL HOUSEHOLDS IN ZONE D AGRO ECOLOGICAL ZONES OF KOGI STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: This study examined farmers' attitudes towards the consumption of fruits and vegetables among rural households.

Design/Methodology: primary data were utilized. A total of 160 respondents were chosen at random for the study. Descriptive statistics, binary logit regression, and mean scores were used to analyse the data collected.

Findings: According to the findings, the majority of respondents were married men and had secondary education. The most common fruits and vegetables that respondents could find and eat were bananas, onions, and oranges. Most of the respondents get fruits and vegetables from their own gardens.

Practical Implications: This study shows that Fruits and vegetables consumption were negatively affected by seasonality, income, unavailability, poor market access, storage facilities, infrastructure facilities, quality, pest and disease and post-harvest losses.

Originality/value: The thrust of this work is premised on the fact that there is a current need to evaluate attitudes of farmers toward consumption of fruits and vegetables that are readily available in the study area. It makes immense contribution to the existing literature on the consumption of fruits and vegetables. The research exposes the fact that fruits and vegetables can be transformed into forms that may be conserved, extending their shelf life and, as a result, making it possible to access them year-round and reducing post-harvest losses in the rural consumers.

Keywords: Attitudes, Consumption, Fruits and Vegetables, Rural households

Paper Type: Research paper

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the main causes of non-communicable diseases and death worldwide is low fruit and vegetable diet (Lim et al., 2013). According to the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), consuming 400 grams of fruit and vegetables each day is a sufficient intake. Insufficient consumption of fruits and vegetables was linked to over 3.9 million deaths worldwide in 2017 (WHO, 2019). According to estimates by Afshin et al. (2019), eating too little fruit and vegetables contributes to 14% of global deaths from gastrointestinal cancer, 11% of deaths from ischemic heart disease, and 9% of deaths from stroke.

The World Health Organization's daily recommendations for fruit and vegetable consumption are not being met in Africa (Hall et al., 2009). According to estimations, sub-Saharan Africans consume between 70 and 312 grams of fruit and vegetables a day, which is much less than the WHO recommended of at least 400 grams (Ruel and Minot, 2005). Numerous nutrients, including vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants, can be found in fruits and vegetables. Consuming the recommended serving sizes of fruits and vegetables daily will give the body the potassium, folate, vitamin A, and vitamin C it needs. Folate aids in the body's production of red blood cells. Folate-rich foods including bell pepper tomatoes, carrots and butter, and nut squash aid to maintain healthy skin and eyes and fight against infections, making them especially beneficial for women of childbearing age (WHO, 2017).

The United States Department of Agriculture has previously found that income, age, and education were the three main variables impacting people's attitudes toward eating fruits and vegetables in general (Diansheng & Lin, 2009). The attitudes of farmers regarding the consumption of fruits and vegetables by rural households in Zone D of the Argo-ecological Zones of Kogi State, Nigeria, must therefore be investigated.

2. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The research specifically aims to:

- Determine the socioeconomic traits of the region's fruit and vegetable consumers.
- Specify the varieties of fruits and vegetables that are typically consumed there.
- Find out how fruits and vegetables are typically consumed in the study area's diet.
- Examine the variables that work against the consumption of fruits and vegetables.
- Identify the sources of fruit and vegetables that are available to the respondents.
- Ascertain the impact of the socioeconomic background of fruit and vegetable consumers on their understanding of nutritional value.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study was carried out in Kogi State's Agro-Ecological Zone D, which has five local government areas: Ibaji, Idah, Igalamela-Odolu, Ofu, and Olamaboro. Its administrative Centre is located in Ofu Local Government Area in Aloma. The region is bordered by the River Niger

on the west, Enugu State on the east, Anambra State on the south, and the North Benue/Nassarawa States on the north. It measures 120 kilometres long and 160 kilometres wide. It occupies a region of around 13,665 square kilometres and is situated roughly between latitudes 06005' and 08000 North and longitudes 06007 and 070.05 East (Ukwedeh, 2003). With nine (5) Local Government Areas, Kogi East Senatorial District has a population of 8,483,373 (NPC, 2006).

The state's Agroecological Zone D's primary residents are the tribes that speak Igala, as well as smaller tribes like the Igbo, Yoruba, Ebira, Hausa, and Bassa. Their primary economic activity is agriculture. They grow cash crops and food crops like coffee, cocoa, palm oil, cashews, mangoes, maize, cassava, yam, and melon, among others, and they raise livestock like sheep, goats, chickens, and birds.

The area has a distinct wet and dry season system and is located in a warm, humid region of Nigeria. Two main air masses—the tropical maritime and the tropical continental—are thus responsible for the region's climate. The tropical savanna woodland of secondary types and combinations of dispersed tropical trees and grassland forms remain the primary vegetation groups in the eastern region, where the mean annual temperature is 24.50C. The dry season and the wet season alternate annually in the study region. April through October is the wet season, and November through March is the dry season. Averaging 1500–2000mm yearly, rainfall is severe throughout the rainy months (Ocholi, 2018).

In the study, a multistage sampling technique was adopted. First, eight cells were chosen at random from Zone's blocks. Second, ten agricultural households were chosen at random from each cell. In the third round, 2 members of any household are purposefully chosen, bringing the total responders to 160. A well-structured questionnaire was used to gather primary data, and information was gathered in accordance with the stated goal. Descriptive statistics, inferential statistics, binary logit regression, and a three-point Likert scale were utilized to examine this research.

With the aid of descriptive statistics like frequency, percentage, mean, and mode, Objectives 1, 2, 3, and 4 were examined.

Binary logit regression was used to evaluate Objective 5.

Using the mean score from a three-point Likert scale, objective 6 was examined.

4. MODEL SPECIFICATION

Binary logit regression;

$$Li = \ln\left(\frac{P}{1-P}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 \dots \dots \dots \beta_nx_n + U_i$$

Li=likelihood of regular consumption of fruits and vegetables. (regular consumption=1, not consuming regularly=0)

P is the likelihood that you regularly eat fruits and vegetables.

1-p is the likelihood that you don't routinely eat fruits and veggies.

β_0 means intercept

estimated parameters = 1 to n

Set of independent variables = X_1 -----n

Mean score

The following will be the three-point Likert scale's mean score, which will be used:

Very Serious 3

Serious 2

Not seriously 1

The following formula was used to determine the mean response to each item.

$$X = \frac{\sum FX}{N}$$

X is the average score, F is the percentage of respondents who chose a particular scale point, X is the scale point's numerical value, N is the total number of respondents, and \sum the summation.

Decision rule

$$\frac{3 + 2 + 1}{3} = \frac{6}{3} = 2$$

Any mean score above 2 was considered serious and constituted a serious problem.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The collected data were analyzed and the results are presented here.

5.1 Social and Economic Traits of the Respondents

The selected socioeconomic traits of the household are described in this part, including the respondents' gender, age, marital status, level of education, occupation, and size of the family.

Table 1: The respondents' distribution based on their socioeconomic traits

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Gender			
Male	92	57.5	
Female	68	42.5	Male
Total	160	100	
Age			
Less than 30	38	23.8	
31 – 40	50	19.4	
41 – 50	31	31.3	44years
51 – 60	10	6.3	
Above 61	31	19.4	
Total	160	100	
Marital status			
Single	1	0.6	
Married	126	78.8	Married
Divorced	9	5.6	
Window	21	13.1	
Missing	3	1.9	
Total	160	100	
Educational level			
Non-informal education	24	15.0	
Primary	34	21.3	
Secondary	52	32.5	Secondary
Tertiary	48	30.0	
Missing	2	1.3	
Total	160	100	
Household size			
Less than 5	68	42.5	7persons
6 – 12	76	47.5	
Above 12	12	7.5	
Missing	4	2.5	
Total	160	100	
Occupation			
Farming	69	43.1	Farming
Trading	46	28.8	
Civil servant	33	20.6	
Retired	12	7.5	
Total	160	100	

Reference: Field Survey, 2022

Gender

Table 1 reveals that the respondents were (42.5%) female and (57.5%) male. This implies that males were dominant as the household head, and between both genders, several traits differentiate them which in turn affects their consumption. This finding agrees with Ojogbo and Alufohia (2010) who asserted majority of the household were male-headed.

Age

The result from Table 1 shows that 31.3% were in the age group of 31- 40, while the mean age of the household in this study was 44 years; this result is consistent with the findings of Taher and Gholam (2009) who noted that the mean age 43.9 years of respondents among farmers who participated in irrigation management in the Doroodzan Dam irrigation Network in Iran. The age group of 51–60 accounted for (6.3%) of the respondents.

Marital status

According to the results, 5.6% of respondents were divorced, 78.8% were married, and 0.6% were single. This implies that married people were expected to eat more fruits and vegetables than single, divorced, and widowed people. This supports a 2012 research by Mazza et al.(2012) that 96.5% of the farmers they studied in Imo state were married.

Education level

According to Table 1 above, a sizable portion of respondents 32.5% of the household head had secondary education, followed by tertiary education (30.0%), primary education (21.3%), and no formal education (15.0%). This suggests that the majority of household heads who are educated eat more fruits and vegetables. The chance of spending money on fruits and vegetables is a result of healthy living, which increases knowledge through education.

Household size

According to Table 1 above, 47.5% of the household respondents had between 6 and 12 people, 42.5% had less than 5, 7.5% had more than 12 people, and the average age of the respondents was 7. This suggests that the six to twelve home group consumes more fruits and vegetables than the other group.

Occupation of the respondents

43.1% of people were farmers, 28.8% were traders, 20.6% were civil servants, and 7.5% were retirees, according to Table 1.

5.2 Types of Fruits and Vegetable Consumption.

Different kinds of fruits and vegetables that the respondents often consumed

Table 2's results showed that banana consumption was highest, followed by onion consumption coming in second, followed by orange consumption coming in third, pepper consumption coming in fourth, tomato consumption coming in fifth, mango coming in sixth, pawpaw coming in seventh, millet coming in eighth, cashews coming in ninth, pineapple coming in tenth, okra coming in eleventh, bitter leaf coming in twelve, cucumber coming in thirteen, water leaves coming in twelfth, fluted pumpkin and coconut coming in twentieth, curry Accordingly, the fruits and vegetables that were most frequently consumed and made available in the study area were the banana, onion, orange, pepper, and mango.

Table 2: A breakdown of the respondents' consumption of different types of fruits and vegetables

Types of fruits/vegetables	No	Yes	Remark
Banana	9	151	1 st
Onion	10	150	2 nd
Orange	20	140	3 rd
Pepper	27	133	4 th
Tomato	30	130	5 th
Mango	32	128	6 th
Pawpaw	39	121	7 th
Millet	44	116	8 th
Cashew	48	112	9 th
Pineapple	51	109	10 th
Okra	59	101	11 th
Bitter leaf	60	100	12 th
Cucumber	70	90	13 th
Water leaves	72	88	14 th
Apple	74	86	15 th
Carrots	75	85	16 th
Water-melon	89	71	17 th
Melon	95	65	18 th
Guava	96	64	19 th
Fluted pumpkin	98	62	20 th
Coconut	98	62	20 th
Curry leaf	102	58	21 st
Spinach	106	53	22 nd
Cabbage	107	53	22 nd
Amaranthus	111	49	23 rd
Eggplant	111	49	23 rd
Garlic	113	47	24 th
Mushroom	116	43	25 th
Pear	118	42	26 th
Drumstick(Moringa oleifera)	120	40	27 th
Cherries	120	40	27 th
Peas	124	36	28 th
Lettuce	126	34	29 th
Avocado	129	31	30 th
Grapes	130	30	30 th
Form of fruits and vegetables mainly consumed	Frequency	Percent	
Cooked	95	59.4%	
Raw	37	23.1%	
Juice	12	7.5%	
Steamed	6	3.8%	

Fried	10	6.3%	
Total	160	100%	
Sources of fruits and vegetables			
Garden	62	38.8%	
Farm gate	29	18.1%	
Market	51	31.9%	
Hawkers/vendors	18	11.3%	
Total	160	100%	

Source; Field Survey, 2022

Primary fruit and vegetable varieties consumed by respondents

As indicated in Table 2 above, reflected that the respondents consumed fruits and vegetables in cooked form (59.4%), 23.1% consumed raw, 7-5% consumed them in the form of juice, 6.3% consumed them in fried form and 3.8% in steamed form. This implies that most of the household consumed fruits and vegetables by cooking them.

Sources of fruits and vegetables

As shown in Table 2 above, shows that the respondents obtained their fruits and vegetables from their garden (38.8%), and 31.9% purchased their fruits and vegetables from the market. 18.1% obtained their fruits and vegetables from the farm gate and 11.3% purchased fruits and vegetables from hawkers/vendors. This supports the conclusion of Billson et al. (2000), who found that people who consumed homegrown food consumed much more fruits and vegetables than people who did not.

Table 3: socioeconomic factors' effects on frequent fruit and vegetable consumption

Variables	Coefficient	P-value
Age	.0326992	0.704
Education	.9758363	0.003***
Income	7.661000	0.072*
Household size	.3065355	0.004***
Gender	.000091	0.998
Access to fruits and vegetables	.1564092	0.732
Constant	-2.174878	0.025
Number of Obs.	160	
Pseudo R-square	0.6908	
Prob>chi square	0.05498	
Lr chi square (6)	26.94	

Data from a field survey, 2022

Note: The likelihood limits for *, **, and * are 10%, 5%, and 1%, accordingly.**

In order to ascertain the relationship between the socioeconomic factors of the respondents and their consumption of fruits and vegetables, Table 3 presents binary logit regression analysis. 10% statistical significance was assigned to the probability chi-square value of (0.05498). As a result,

the alternative hypothesis was accepted and the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that among all the explanatory variables in the model, household size, education, and income were found to have a significant impact on the respondents' likelihood of regularly consuming fruits and vegetables. As a consequence, the regression model's independent variables were shown to account for 69.08% of the variation in the respondents' likelihood of regularly consuming fruits and vegetables.

According to the likelihood-ratio chi-squared test result (26.94), the models are able to accurately predict the differences in the probability of socioeconomic features on rural household regular consumption of fruits and vegetables.

At 1%, the coefficient of schooling was substantial and positive. This implies that the respondents' likelihood of consistently consuming fruits and vegetables increases with their degree of education. This outcome can be explained by the fact that education makes people aware of the health advantages of various kinds of fruits and vegetables.

At the 10% level, the coefficient of income was determined to be favorable and significant. This suggests that the likelihood of a household consuming more fruits and vegetables will rise as its income does. Similar findings among Turkish students were found by Usman (2004) as well.

A 1% significant level positive coefficient for household size was found. This indicates that respondents in the research area will be more likely to consume fruits and vegetables if there are more households. This is in line with Minot's (2002) assertion that households in Viet Nam with a higher percentage of older children allocated larger portions of their budget to fruits and vegetables.

Table 4: Variables that work against the consumption of fruits and vegetables

Constraints	Very serious	Serious	Not serious	Mean	Remark
Seasonality	123	27	10	2.71	Serious
Income	88	39	33	2.34	Serious
Unavailability	122	26	12	2.69	Serious
Poor market access	114	30	16	2.61	Serious
Storage facility	121	17	22	2.62	Serious
Infrastructural facility	124	25	11	2.71	Serious
Quality	118	29	13	2.66	Serious
Pest and diseases	124	21	15	2.68	Serious
Post-harvest losses	124	20	16	2.68	Serious
Types of fruits and vegetables	18	32	110	1.43	Not serious

Reference: Field Survey, 2022

Seasonality, with a mean of 2.71, was seen as a significant limitation, as shown in Table 4 above. Fruits and vegetables are extremely perishable, and there aren't enough storage facilities to lengthen their shelf lives and make them more readily available all year. This supports Orishagbemi's assertion from 2014 that seasonality and a lack of post-harvest facilities shorten the shelf life of highly perishable foods.

With a mean of 2.34, income is a factor in how much produce is consumed. Inferred from this is that because fruits and vegetables must be purchased with money, a change in income may result in a drop in the intake of these foods. This supports the claim made by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC), 2003, that rising incomes will improve consumers' desire for fruits and vegetables.

Consumption of fruits and vegetables with a mean of 2.69 was considered severely constrained by the lack of availability. implies that because of their seasonality, fruit and vegetables were not available all year long.

With a mean of 2.61, poor market access is another issue limiting the consumption of fruits and vegetables. As a result of the seasonal nature of the products, there is not a year-round market for fruits and vegetables. This concurs with Rehima's (2006) study, which found that among the factors affecting supply are market access, production level, extension contact, and market intelligence.

The storage facility was considered among the factor with a mean of 2.67 confronting consumption of fruits and vegetables. This implies that there was inadequate medium of storing fruits and vegetables. This agrees with Orishagbemi, (2014).

A serious comment was made about the infrastructure facility, which had a mean of 2.71. In other words, a lack of infrastructure amenities has a detrimental effect on the intake of fruits and vegetables.

With a mean of 2.68, pests, illnesses, and post-harvest losses are additional issues with the eating of fruits and vegetables. It follows that pests and diseases have an impact on the quality of fruits and vegetables. After harvest time, the majority of fruits and vegetables are lost because they are fragile in nature.

6. CONCLUSION

The majority of the responders were men, according to this study's findings. The respondents' frequent eating of fruits and vegetables is also positively impacted by household size, income, and education. The vast majority of respondents ate cooked fruits and vegetables.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following suggestions were made as a result;

1. To increase the intake of fruits and vegetables, there should be greater public education on the medical advantages of doing so, as well as a rise in farmer earnings.
2. Farmers should be encouraged to practice off-season cropping (through irrigation) of fruits and vegetables so there will be availability of fruits and vegetables all year round.
3. There is also a need to promote storage technologies which would preserve freshness as well as nutritional contents of fruits and vegetables.
4. Garden/ backyard farming of fruits and vegetables should be encouraged among farmers.
5. Fruit transformation into varieties that can be preserved should be the primary concern. Fruits will be typically available and reasonably priced as a result, and losses following harvest will be decreased.

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